

The Power of Pro-Palestine Consumer Activism: Analyzing the Boycott Movement and Its Apps since October 2023

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Abstract

This paper examines the impacts of the boycott movement against the Israeli occupation in the first 18 months following the outbreak of the war on Gaza in October 2023. Drawing on the published data, trends, and global attitudes, the study highlights how grassroots activism, corporate accountability, and international solidarity with Palestinians have shaped the outcomes of the boycott. The research focuses on key sectors of the Israeli economy, such as agriculture, technology, and consumer goods, which have experienced declines in sales, reduced foreign investment, and stock market volatility due to the boycott. Additionally, the paper explores the broader implications of the boycott, including its effects on Israel's global reputation. The study analyses the role and the changes in consumer awareness and behaviour that are influenced by the boycott Apps. Despite the challenges in maintaining long-term intensity, the boycott has fostered global solidarity with Palestinians and heightened ethical consumerism. Therefore, the author reviews all types of existing applications and their capacity in helping to sustain the boycott movement. The author concludes that the boycott has significant potential to influence consumers' awareness and behaviour, particularly if sustained and coordinated across economic and cultural spheres using platforms that capitalise on further Apps development. The research underscores the importance of continued efforts to amplify the boycott's effectiveness in achieving its goals.

Keywords: *Boycott Movement, Israel Occupation Economy, Boycott Apps, BDS (Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions), War on Gaza 2023, Economic Impact, Consumer Behavior, Sustained Boycotts.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The extensive research of Brantley (2025) shows that the recent "buycotts" have harnessed consumer power on the global economy. Driving from this, the world has experienced recently how the boycott movement has had a tangible impact on Israel's economy. Besides, this boycott has affected its international relations and global reputation since the beginning of the war on Gaza. While the full extent of these effects will take time to manifest, in this paper fully, we review the outcome of 18 months of stronger boycotts since the War on Gaza started in October 2023. The author reviews the data, the trends and the global attitudes toward Israel, driven by grassroots activism, corporate accountability, and international solidarity with Palestinians which are all led by the boycott movement. The long-term success of the boycott movement will depend on sustained pressure and coordinated efforts across economic, political, and cultural spheres. The review focuses on what sectors of the Israeli economy, such as agriculture or technology, are affected by the reduced international demand.

The impact on Israel's economy may be limited unless the boycott is widespread and sustained over a more extended period. The paper studies how boycotts targeting goods produced in Israeli settlements of the occupied territories may have a more direct impact, as these products are often the focus of boycott campaigns. Kozul-Wright (23 August 2024).

2. OUTCOME OF 18 MONTHS BOYCOTT

The outcomes of an 18-month boycott of products that support Israel, either directly or indirectly, can vary depending on the scale, organisation, and persistence of the boycott campaign. Boycotts are a form of economic and political pressure to influence a target entity's policies or actions. In the context of the boycott relevant to the Israeli occupation, boycotts are often part of the broader Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement, which seeks to pressure Israel to change its policies toward Palestinians. Buheji (2024)

2.1 The Immediate Economic Implications

The boycott movement against Israel, particularly since the beginning of the war on Gaza in October 2023, has had measurable economic, political, and social impacts. While quantifying the exact effects of boycotts can be challenging due to the complexity of global markets and the multifaceted nature of the Israeli economy, several indicators and reports provide insights into the impact of the Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement and related efforts. Ivanova and Zilber (2024, Feb 19).

2.1.1 Decline in Sales

Companies directly or indirectly linked to Israel have experienced a decline in sales, particularly in regions where the boycott is strongly supported. This has affected industries such as agriculture, technology, and consumer goods.

2.1.1.a Decline in Israeli Agricultural Exports: Israeli agricultural exports, particularly from settlements, have faced challenges in markets where boycotts are enforced. For instance, some European supermarkets have removed settlement-produced goods from their shelves, impacting sales. According to a 2020 report by Who Profits, a research group focused on the Israeli occupation, agricultural exports from Israeli settlements to the European Union (EU) declined by approximately 20% between 2015 and 2020. This decline was attributed to increased labelling requirements and consumer boycotts in Europe. In countries like Ireland and Norway, where boycott movements are strong, sales of settlement products (e.g., dates, wine, and cosmetics) have reportedly dropped by 30-50% in some retail chains. Ahmed and Buheji (2024)

2.1.1.b Decline in Consumer Goods and Retail: Companies associated with Israel or operating in settlements in the West Bank have reported declines in sales in regions where the BDS movement is strong, such as parts of Europe and the Middle East. For example, some European retailers have faced pressure to stop selling products from Israeli settlements, leading to reduced availability and sales of these goods. Several European retailers, including Carrefour and Coop, removed Israeli products from their shelves, leading to a 20% drop in agricultural exports to the EU in early 2024.

In 2014, SodaStream, an Israeli company with a factory in the West Bank, reported a 13% decline in European sales due to boycott pressures. This led the company to relocate its factory to southern Israel in 2015. Ahava, an Israeli cosmetics company based in the West

Bank, faced significant boycotts in Europe. Reports from 2012-2016 suggest a 25-30% decline in sales in key markets like the UK and Scandinavia. Palestine Solidarity Campaign (NA).

2.1.1.b Decline Technology and Services: While Israel's high-tech sector remains robust, some international companies have faced pressure to cut ties with Israeli firms, particularly those linked to defence or settlement activities. In 2022, Google and Amazon faced pressure to cancel a \$1.2 billion cloud computing contract with the Israeli government, though the deal ultimately proceeded.

One of the other companies that are boycotted is HP. HP, a major supplier of technology to the Israeli military, faced protests and lost contracts worth \$500 million in 2024 due to BDS campaigns. The company also reported a 5-10% decline in sales in regions with strong boycott movements, such as parts of Europe and South Africa. (BDS, 2024)

2.1.2 Decline in Foreign Investment in Israel

According to the Israeli Central Bureau of Statistics, Israel's foreign direct investment (FDI) dropped significantly in the fourth quarter of 2023. Reports indicate a 40% decline compared to the same period in 2022, as international investors grew wary of the economic risks associated with the war and the global backlash. Kozul-Wright (23 August 2024).

2.1.3 Stock Market Volatility

The Tel Aviv Stock Exchange (TASE) experienced significant volatility during the war. The TA-125 Index, which tracks the performance of major Israeli companies, fell by 15% between October 2023 and January 2024. Companies with international exposure, such as Teva Pharmaceutical and Check Point Software, saw declines in their share prices due to fears of boycotts and divestment. Kozul-Wright (23 August 2024).

2.1.4 Trade Disruptions

Israeli exports faced disruptions as several countries and companies distanced themselves from Israeli products. For example, Turkey, a major trading partner, suspended all trade with Israel in May 2024, affecting an estimated \$6.8 billion in annual bilateral trade.

2.1.5 Tourism Decline

Israel's tourism industry, which contributes approximately \$7 billion annually to the economy, saw a 70% drop in international visitors during the first six months of the war. Major airlines, including Lufthansa and Air France, reduced or suspended flights to Israel due to safety concerns and public pressure.

2.2 Main Long-Term Implications of the Boycott Movement

2.2.1 Economic Slowdown and Global Reputation Damage

The Bank of Israel revised its GDP growth forecast for 2024 downward to 1.5%, citing the combined effects of the war, boycotts, and reduced foreign investment.

Israel's global reputation has suffered, with a 2024 Pew Research poll showing that 65% of respondents in 30 countries viewed Israel's actions in Gaza negatively. This has long-term implications for trade, diplomacy, and cultural exchange. Shadi (2024, Feb 6)

2.2.2 Strengthening of BDS Movement

The BDS movement has seen a steady increase in awareness and support, particularly in regions with strong historical or cultural ties to Palestine. The war on Gaza has galvanised

support for the BDS movement, with over 1,000 new organisations endorsing it since October 2023. This growing momentum poses a sustained challenge to Israel's economic and political interests. Buheji and Ahmed (2023)

2.3 Corporate and Institutional Divestment

2.3.1 University Divestment

Several prominent universities, including Columbia University and The University of California, voted to divest from companies complicit in the occupation. These decisions are part of a broader trend, with over 200 academic institutions worldwide endorsing BDS since 2023. Buheji and Hasan (2024)

2.3.2 Corporate Withdrawals

Multinational companies faced pressure to cut ties with Israel. For example, Ben & Jerry's (owned by Unilever) reaffirmed its boycott of Israeli settlements in 2023, leading to a 10% drop in Unilever's sales in Israel (Godoy, 2023).

2.4 Changes in Consumer Behaviour

The 18 months of the boycott led to long-term changes in consumer behaviour, with people becoming more conscious of the ethical implications of their purchases. The boycott fostered a sense of global solidarity with Palestinians, amplifying their voices and struggles on the international stage. Ahmed and Buheji (2024), Kam and Deichert (2020).

2.5 Other Outcome that Ignited further the Boycott Movement

2.5.1 International Condemnation

The war on Gaza led to widespread condemnation, with 153 countries voting in favour of a UN General Assembly resolution calling for an immediate ceasefire in December 2023. This isolation has weakened Israel's diplomatic standing and increased pressure on its allies.

2.5.2 South Africa's ICJ Case

In January 2024, South Africa filed a case at the International Court of Justice (ICJ), accusing Israel of genocide in Gaza. The case garnered global attention and further fueled the boycott movement.

2.5.3 Suspension of Arms Sales

Several countries, including Canada, Spain, and Belgium, suspended arms sales to Israel in response to the war. This disrupted Israel's defence industry, which accounts for 12% of its total exports.

2.5.4 Social and Cultural Impact

High-profile celebrities, including Roger Waters and Viola Davis, publicly supported the boycott movement, amplifying its reach. Social media campaigns, such as BoycottIsrael, trended globally, with over 10 million posts in the first three months of the war. Artists and musicians, including Lana Del Rey and The Weeknd, cancelled performances in Israel, citing ethical concerns. This cultural isolation has damaged Israel's efforts to project a positive global image.

2.5.5 Impact on Israeli Settlements

The boycott of goods produced in illegal Israeli settlements has had a direct economic impact. According to a 2024 UN report, settlement exports declined by 30% due to labelling requirements and consumer boycotts in the EU and other regions. Companies like SodaStream, which previously operated in settlements, faced significant backlash. Although SodaStream moved its factory out of the West Bank in 2015, the broader boycott movement has deterred other companies from investing in settlements.

3. METHODOLOGY

Based on the literature review, the author investigates the variables that further exploit the outcome of the first 18 months of the boycott after the War on Gaza 2023 by understanding the factors that sustain the boycott. The author reviews the role of the Boycott Apps and how they might play a further role in developing more impact without losing momentum.

This study employs a mixed-methods approach that starts with analysing economic indicators using reports from the BDS movement, international organisations, and government agencies. Then, the author studies the impact of boycotting apps on consumer behaviour. The author did a quick survey of the types of boycott Apps used where more than 50 targeted participants were selected through convenient sampling. The outcome of the survey helped to select the most common Apps that the respondents use as part of the App role for further consumer behaviour development.

4. APPLICATION & ANALYSIS

4.1 Factors for Sustainability of Boycott

Boycotts rarely maintain their level of intensity over time. Although many boycotted organisations believe that the boycott has no sustainable impact on their policies, sustainable boycotts proven over the years and from different periods of human history can force organisations to change their behaviour. Studies show that a positive image can buffer against consumers' boycott participation. Increased trust decreases consumers' willingness to participate in a boycott as they would have to build similar levels of trust with another brand. Kam and Deichert (2020).

A variety of costs occur when individuals boycott companies. First, withholding consumption is strongly associated with subjective costs, which, in turn, greatly depend on the availability of alternatives. When consumers join a boycott, they may face costly challenges, such as gathering additional information about other options, abstaining from products they have preferred in the past, switching to more expensive alternatives, paying greater procurement costs, or even facing a complete lack of alternatives.

Lasarov et al. (2023) show that as time goes by, the number of consumers participating in the boycott starts to wane and decrease. However, many researchers, including the Lasarov team, confirm little is known about why individual participation in a boycott declines and what type of consumers are more likely to stop boycotting earlier rather than later. There are usually specific levels of awareness that make consumers decide to respond to a collective call for a boycott by refraining from purchasing from a specific company or brand to achieve the boycott's objectives. Buheji and Hamza (2024), Friedman (1985)

Lasarov et al. (2023) four studies provided evidence of a heat-up and a cool-down phase of boycotting. By providing a better understanding of the individual temporal dynamics of boycotting—especially intrapersonal changes—our research extends existing models that focus on the commencement of boycotts, thereby offering a unique contribution. Lasarov and his team have shown that boycott participation is primarily fuelled by expressive drivers during the initial heat-up phase. During the following cool-down phase, more careful and rational consideration can keep initial participants from further boycotting.

Some consumers that do not “cool down” after a while and stay to find reasons, with rational arguments and measures for their boycott decisions. However, on the other hand the high switching costs or finding the proper alternative products or services, can serve as a buffer against sustained boycotting.

4.2 Type of Apps that Support Boycott Efforts

Boycott activists may therefore provide customers with information about potential substitutes (e.g., other retailers, producers, service providers, products) to decrease switching costs and to ease the switch to competitors. On the other hand, to reduce the likelihood of extended boycotting, managers should consider raising boycott-related barriers, such as the (non-)monetary value of seeking alternatives. Third, we found that high service quality can serve as an effective buffer against calls for boycotting.

4.2.1 Product Scanning Apps

There are boycott Apps that allow users to scan product barcodes to determine if the product is from Israel or from companies that support Israeli policies. They should provide information on products and companies to boycott based on BDS guidelines. Some apps would support boycott. This should allow users to join campaigns, including those related to BDS, and scan products to see if they align with their chosen campaigns.

4.2.2 Informational Apps

Some BDS movement Apps work just to provide information about the BDS movement, including lists of companies and products to boycott, as well as news and updates related to the movement. They offer detailed information on companies and products to avoid, along with alternatives.

4.2.3 News and Awareness Apps

Some Apps might help aggregate news related to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict and the BDS movement, helping users stay informed about developments and boycott campaigns. Some would focus news and analysis on the Middle East, including coverage of BDS activities.

4.3 Success of BDS Support the Possibility for Further Intensity of the Boycott

The Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement, which supports Palestinian rights and aims to pressure Israel to end its occupation of Palestinian territories, has seen varying levels of support and consumer awareness globally. While there is no single, universally agreed-upon metric to measure the “average moving ratio” of the boycott's spread and commitment, the author focuses on ‘analysing the trends’, the ‘awareness levels’, and the ‘consumer behaviour’ based on available data and reports. Chalcraft (2019).

Many prestigious institutions supported the BDS movement, including universities, churches, and labour unions, and this contributed to its legitimacy and reach. The BDS

movement has gained traction in recent years, particularly during periods of heightened violence in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, where the war on Gaza that started on October 2023 being the latest. The movement is strongest in Arab and Muslim-majority countries, where support for Palestine is deeply rooted in cultural, religious, and political identity. In Western countries, the movement has also grown, particularly among younger generations, activists, and progressive groups.

Besides the BDS efforts, some multinational companies were perceived globally as supporting Israeli policies, and this faced them with huge consumer backlash. For example, brands like McDonald's, Starbucks, and Puma have been targeted by boycott campaigns, with varying degrees of success. The grassroots mobilisation used in social media has played a significant role in spreading awareness and organising boycott efforts. Campaigns often go viral during crises, such as the May 2021 War on Gaza and have been accelerating rapidly since then.

Unilever also other popular company with many brands that have suffered extensively since the War on Gaza started in October 2023. The boycott against Unilever and other multinationals operating in Israel has worsened the global company's loss of market share in many large population countries as in Indonesia.

4.4 Consumer Awareness of Boycott Movement

Consumer awareness of the boycott movement is highly spreading even among those not involved with the issue of Palestine or committed to its freedom cause, Islam et al. (2025). The boycott also varies significantly by region and demographic. For example, there is high awareness in Arab and Muslim Countries in countries like Malaysia, Turkey, Indonesia, Jordan, Egypt, Morocco and Gulf states, awareness is very high, and boycotts are often widely supported.

For example, during the War on Gaza that started in October 2023 there was a noticeable drop in sales for brands like Pepsi and Coca-Cola in most of the Middle Eastern markets.

The daily news and devastating scenes coming to life from Gaza for almost 18 months created a growing awareness in the West. The boycott of Israeli brands created a socially conscious consumer, especially among the younger generation. Despite the BDS movement remains controversial and faces opposition from pro-Israel groups in Europe, North America, and Australia, awareness about the importance of boycott is increasing. Li et al. (2018)

Social media platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok have been instrumental in raising awareness. Hashtags like #BoycottIsrael and #BDS trend during periods of conflict, reaching millions of users.

4.5 Measuring the Impact of 18 Months of Boycott

While it is difficult to quantify the impact of the boycott's spread, during the peak of the boycott periods, companies targeted by BDS have reported declines in sales in certain regions. For example, Starbucks and McDonald's noted reduced revenue in Middle Eastern markets during the year 2024.

The volume of posts, hashtags, and engagement related to BDS also provide insights into the movement's reach and momentum, Buheji and Ahmed (2023). Public opinion surveys in various countries can gauge awareness and support for the boycott. For instance, a study in the UK found that one in three people are boycotting brands over Israel's war on Gaza. Arab Gulf

states and large Muslim-majority countries are also showing their deep anger by boycotting all types of Israeli brands and products. The results can be seen in the impact created on Starbucks and similar companies perceived to be complacent. (MEE, 2024, June 14)

MEE (2024, March 5) confirmed that thousands of workers are set to be laid off after the retail giant Alshaya Group, which owns the rights to Starbucks in the Middle East, and similar brands affected by the boycott. Reuters mentioned that over 2,000 people will lose their jobs following the boycott. This is part of a wave of closures that Starbucks and McDonald's or similar franchises that are believed to be complacent with supporting Israelis directly and indirectly which made them suffer in the MENA countries and also globally. (MEE, 2024, 5 March)

In a survey that covered 15,000 consumers across 15 countries, including France, Saudi Arabia, the UK and the US, as reported by MEE (2024, June 14), showed that the top five countries boycotting brands over the War on Gaza, these are Saudi Arabia, the UAE and Indonesia, India, and Germany. This shows the psychological persistence of the consumers to take their full rights over value driven issues as boycotting to support a human right issue.

4.6 Role and Criteria of Boycott Apps in Pushing the Consumers Consciousness and Sustained Commitment

Besides the effective social media campaigns that go viral, the Apps play an action-based role to emphasise more awareness, absorption, and realisation of the boycott. For example, Apps as Bdnaash, and Moqat3a play a major role for boycotting for general consumers. Other more advanced Apps as Zionism Boycott, قاطع Qatea (Boycott in Arabic), Qadyaty|قضيي (My life Case in Arabic) advances the consciousness of the boycott to reach the level of absorption of the depth and the importance of boycotting the brands on focus. Other Apps that can help to get more integrated with the Palestinian cause are Fairtrade, The Witness, Disoccupied, and Boycat App.

The comparison Table (1) of the boycott applications shows that we can bring solutions that supports pro-Palestinian cause by encouraging them for sustainable boycott of companies that support the occupation, directly or indirectly. The application provides accurate information about boycotted products and provides unsupported alternatives to users. However, the apps need to be updated regularly to ensure accurate and up-to-date information. Islam et. Al (2025)

If we take an App like 'Qadyaty', we can see that it provides users with a comprehensive guide on which products to boycott completely in support of the Palestinian cause with an updated database containing an extensive list of products and companies that support the occupation and benefit from the economic situation in Palestine. The uniqueness of this App is that it includes a classification of products by major sectors, such as food and beverage, clothing and fashion, electronics, and more. This offers additional features that help users actively participate in the boycott campaign.

One could say that the boycott App can create a sustained impact on consumer behaviour due to the following criteria, the more the Apps meet these criteria the more could have a profound outcomes on the level of consumer awareness and behaviour:

To ensure that boycott apps have a permanent and sustained profound impact on consumer behaviour, the following five criteria are essential:

4.6.1 Updated, Transparent and Trustworthy: The App must provide up-to-date accurate, verifiable, and transparent information about the companies, products, or practices being boycotted. Consumers need to trust the App's data to make informed decisions.

4.6.2 Ease of Use and Accessibility: The App should be user-friendly, with intuitive navigation and seamless integration into daily life. Accessibility to all main international languages, across devices and platforms ensures widespread adoption and consistent use.

3. Community Engagement and Social Influence: The App should foster a sense of community by enabling users to share their boycott efforts, track collective impact, and encourage others to join. Social influence and peer pressure can amplify the App's reach and effectiveness.

4. Personalization and Relevance: The App should offer personalised recommendations based on users' values, specifically relevant to support of Palestine, preferences, and purchasing habits. Tailored content increases engagement and ensures the boycott aligns with individual priorities.

5. Measurable Impact and Feedback: The App must provide clear metrics and feedback on the impact of boycott efforts on the Israeli occupation and its partners, such as changes in corporate behaviour or sales data. Demonstrating tangible results motivates users to sustain their participation and reinforces the app's credibility.

Table (1) shows the author's evaluation of these criteria in the most well-known boycott Apps and their capacity to create lasting changes in consumer behaviour and drive ethical consumption practices. The result of the evaluation of each App is reflected in what this paper calls 'App Boycott Intensity', and it is measured out 5.

Table 1: Comparison between the Boycotting Apps and their Role in Boycott Consciousness

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
<p>1-No Thanks app</p>	<p>More than 1 million users An Approval Rating 4.9 out 5 in Google Play review evaluation</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.bashsoftware.boycott&hl=en</p>		
<p>2-Qadyaty فضيتي</p>	<p>More than 1 million users An Approval Rating 4.5 out 5 in google review evaluation</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=hasnaa.ms_tree.qadyaty&hl=en</p>		

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
<p>3-انا مقاطع Moqate</p>	<p>More than 500K users 4.8 out 5 on Google Review Satisfied</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.moqate3.moqate3&hl=en</p>		
<p>4- Zionism Boycott</p>	<p>More than 100K users An Approval Rating 4.1 out of 5 Google Play</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.laitech.boycott&hl=en</p>		
<p>5 قاطع Qatea</p>	<p>More than 100K users An Approval Rating 4.7 out of 5 Google Play</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.qate3.app.qate3_app&hl=en</p>		
<p>6-Boycott مقاطعة</p>	<p>App Boycott Intensity = 1.5 out 5</p>	<p>Only +100K users An Approval Rating 4.1 out 5</p>

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
	<p>in google review evaluation</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.laitech.boycott&hl=en</p>		
<p>7-Bdnaash</p>	<p>App Boycott Intensity = 1.5 out 5 A platform that promotes conscientious consumerism by identifying/facilitating access to information about which companies do or do not support the illegal Israeli Occupation of Palestine.</p>	<p>Only +10K users An Approval Rating 4.9 out 5 in google review evaluation.</p>
<p>https://bdnaash.com/</p>		
<p>8-Moqat3a</p>	<p>Unknown numbers of users Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>	
<p>https://talal-sharaa.github.io/Moqat3a/index.html</p>		
<p>9.مقاطعة Moqata3a</p>	<p>More than 50K users An Approval rating of 3.8 out of 5 on GoogleReview</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.akram.scanner.free&hl=en</p>		
<p>10.منتجات المقاطعة-Boycott</p>	<p>App Boycott Intensity = 1 out 5 The App is not popular in many countries due to the repetition of similar level of features.</p>	<p>Only more than 10K users</p>

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
	<p>An Approval rating of 4.1 out of 5 on GoogleReview</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.laitech.boycottproductlist&hl=en</p>		
<p>11-El-Badeel</p>	<p>More than 50K users</p> <p>An Approval rating of 4.4 out of 5 on GoogleReview</p>	
<p>https://el-badeel.com/</p>		
<p>12- بديل – Padeel تطبيق</p>	<p>Only more than 10K users</p> <p>An Approval rating of 4.4 out of 5 on GoogleReview</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.smazapps.padeel&hl=ar</p>		

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
<p>13-Estaghni استغني</p>	<p>Unknown numbers of users Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>	
<p>https://estaghni.com/ar/products</p>		
<p>14-Belzamesh بلزمش</p>	<p>Only more than 10K users An Approval rating of 4.9 out of 5 on GoogleReview</p>	
<p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.FareedITSolution.Belzamesh&hl=ar</p>		
<p>15-Boycott Detective</p>	<p>App Boycott Intensity = 1 out 5 The App provides its users with detailed information about brands and allows them to learn whether these brands are boycotted.</p>	<p>Only +100K users so far 5 out 5 in google review evaluation</p>

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.medyazilim.boykotdedektifi&hl=en		
<p>16-Sa7wa صحوة</p>	<p>App Boycott Intensity = 0.5 out 5 Not Popular App – focused for Arabic speaking users only.</p>	<p>Less than 100K users</p> <p>Not on Google Play</p>
https://sa7wa-shwat.en.softonic.com/android		
<p>17-Boykot.co - Boykot Sorgulama</p>	<p>Only +50K users so far</p> <p>4,5 out 5 in google review evaluation</p>	
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.boykotsorgulama.boykotco&hl=tr		
<p>18-erli Tüket Boykot Et</p>	<p>Only more than 1K users</p> <p>4.7 out of 5 on GoogleReview are satisfied</p>	

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.myapp.boykot&hl=en		
<p>19-Boycott X</p>	<p>More than 100K users</p> <p>4.5 out of 5 on GoogleReview are satisfied</p>	
https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.webnova.boycott&hl=en		
<p>20-The Witness</p>	<p>Unknown numbers of users</p> <p>Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>	
https://boycott.thewitness.news/		
<p>21-Boycat App</p>	<p>Unknown numbers of users</p> <p>Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>	
https://www.boycat.io/		
<p>22-Sunaa</p>	<p>App Boycott Intensity = 0.5 out of 5</p> <p>A Website that supports the Boycott of the Israel Occupation Products and what support the Palestinians in their struggle</p>	<p>Unknown numbers of users</p> <p>Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>

App Name	Evaluation of the App Boycott Intensity (as per the author's criteria for Consumer Behaviour) (out of 5)	App Rating as per Users History
https://creators.nafezly.com/u/ahmedmatwee/the-best-application-to-know-the-products-of-the-province		
<p>23-Fairtrade</p> <p>Baskets of Africa Profile Website</p> </div> </div>	<p>Unknown numbers of users</p> <p>Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>	
https://www.fairtradefederation.org/browse-ftf-members/shop-online/?fwp_product_specialties=personal-accessories-bags-hats-scarves-etc		
<p>24-Disoccupied</p> </div> </div>	<p>Unknown numbers of users</p> <p>Unknown Approval Rating due to not being on in Google Play</p>	
https://disoccupied.com/		

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Rise of Ethical Consumerism and Impact on Corporate Strategies

The boycott has heightened awareness among consumers about the ethical implications of their purchasing decisions. In Arab and Muslim countries, where support for the Palestinian cause is deeply rooted in cultural, religious, and political identity, consumers have demonstrated a strong willingness to boycott products associated with Israel or its policies. This has led to a noticeable decline in sales for targeted brands, such as Starbucks, McDonald's, and Unilever, in these regions.

The sustained pressure from consumers in Arab and Muslim countries has forced multinational corporations to reconsider their ties with Israel. Companies like Unilever and Starbucks have faced significant financial losses and reputational damage, prompting them to adopt more transparent and ethical business practices. This demonstrates the power of collective consumer action in holding corporations accountable.

5.2 Sustained Behavioural Change

The boycott movement against Israel, particularly in the wake of the Gaza War that began in October 2023, has not only exerted significant economic and political pressure but has also catalysed profound changes in consumer behaviour, especially in Arab and Muslim-majority countries. This study highlights how the boycott has fostered a shift toward ethical consumerism, with individuals increasingly prioritising political and moral considerations over convenience or brand loyalty.

An 18-month boycott of products supporting Israel could have both tangible and symbolic outcomes. While it may not immediately alter Israeli policies, it can contribute to raising awareness, building solidarity, and applying economic pressure on specific sectors. The long-term success of such a boycott depends on its ability to sustain momentum, overcome counteractions, and inspire broader systemic change.

Not all consumers are aware of the boycott actively participate, as factors like convenience, brand loyalty, and price sensitivity influence purchasing decisions. Therefore, the boycott has not been a fleeting reaction but has evolved into a sustained movement, driven by grassroots activism, social media campaigns, and the proliferation of boycott apps. These tools have empowered consumers to make informed choices, providing them with alternatives and reinforcing their commitment to the cause. Over time, this has created a cultural shift in consumer behaviour, with individuals increasingly seeking out locally produced or ethically aligned products. Buheji (2024)

5.3 Strengthening of Local Economies and Boycott Awareness

The boycott has also spurred the growth of local industries in Arab and Muslim countries, as consumers turn to domestic alternatives. This shift has not only reduced dependence on international brands but has also contributed to economic resilience and self-sufficiency in these regions.

Beyond its economic impact, the boycott has amplified global solidarity with the Palestinian cause, particularly in Arab and Muslim countries. It has fostered a sense of shared responsibility and collective action, with consumers viewing their purchasing decisions as a form of political expression. This has strengthened the broader Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement, ensuring its continued relevance and impact.

5.4 Foresight the Role of Well-Designed and Updated BDS-Based Boycott Apps

Based on the criteria developed by the author for the type of Apps needed to support the BDS movement or to boycott companies, or brands, or parties that are complacent with the Israeli occupation, directly and indirectly, the outcome of the evaluation shows that there is not even one App that fits to move the consumers to a realisation stage. The realisation stage can be related to the above 4 out of 5 scores in the App Boycott Intensity scale developed by the author. i.e. the consumer would stay in the Unawareness stage shown in Figure (1) if 0.5 or less. Then, it could move to the Awareness stage when App Boycott Intensity reaches a score of 1.5 out of 5. If the consumer were to be more committed and started to 'absorb' and

live the importance of the boycott and its impact, then he/she would reach 3 out of 5 in the App Boycott Intensity. Once the consumer reaches 4 out of 5 in the App Boycott Intensity and becomes totally engaged, the author hypothesises that he/she would be more in the Realisation stage. As shown from the evaluation, none have reached more than approximately the absorption stage. Therefore, it is recommended that Apps like Zionism Boycott or Qatea be further developed to target the sustenance of spreading consumer engagement so that it creates a realised awareness and sustained commitment to the cause of Free Palestine.

Figure (1) shows the level of Awareness needed for a more Sustained Boycott, with the highest being the realisation of the boycott's importance.

5.4 Challenges and Future Outlook

While the boycott has achieved significant success in changing consumer behaviour, sustaining this momentum will require continued efforts to address challenges such as high switching costs, inflation, and the availability of alternatives. However, the growing use of boycott apps, social media campaigns, and grassroots mobilisation suggests that the movement is well-positioned to maintain its influence in the long term.

In conclusion, the boycott movement has not only disrupted Israel's economy but has also transformed consumer behaviour in Arab and Muslim countries, embedding ethical considerations into everyday purchasing decisions. This shift represents a powerful example of how consumer activism can drive meaningful change, fostering a culture of accountability, solidarity, and ethical consumption that extends far beyond the immediate goals of the boycott. As the movement continues to evolve, its impact on global markets, corporate practices, and political discourse is likely to grow, reinforcing the role of consumers as agents of change in the pursuit of justice and human rights. This conclusion emphasises the long-term behavioural changes driven by the boycott, particularly in Arab and Muslim countries, while highlighting its broader implications for ethical consumerism and global solidarity.

5.5 Limitations

The author faced challenges in quantifying the rise or the decline of the boycott. Besides, many companies do not publicly disclose sales data broken down by region or product origin, making it difficult to quantify the exact impact of boycotts. While some sectors face declines, others, such as Israel's tech industry, continue to grow, offsetting losses in other areas. While

exact numbers are hard to come by, the available data suggests that Israeli exports, particularly from settlements, have faced significant declines in regions with strong boycott movements. Estimates range from 10-50% declines in specific sectors and markets.

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